

Asghari, H. (2023). The attractiveness of the industrial technology program among newly arrived students in Sweden. In V. Tütlys, L. Vaitkutė & C. Nägele (Eds.), *Vocational Education and Training Transformations for Digital, Sustainable and Socially Fair Future. Proceedings of the 5th Crossing Boundaries Conference in Vocational Education and Training, Kaunas, 25. – 26. May* (pp. 23–29). European Research Network on Vocational Education and Training, VETNET, Vytautas Magnus University Education Academy, Institute of Educational Science. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7808066>

The Attractiveness of the Industrial Technology Program among Newly Arrived Students in Sweden

Asghari, Hamid

hamid.asghari@kau.se, University of Karlstad

Abstract

The Swedish Ministry of Education and Research shows that interest in the Industrial Technology program, an upper secondary vocational education, is decreasing among young people in Sweden (SOU, 2020:33). Fewer applicants also mean fewer trained professionals in the industry. Since the industry is dependent on competent personnel, I am interested in investigating the attractiveness of the Industrial Technology program in Sweden with a special focus on newly arrived students. The methodological starting point of the study is based on Life course research (Elder et al., 2003; Vogt, 2018), and eight newly arrived students' narrated life experiences are combined with Bourdieu's (1985) habitus theory to understand their choice of the Industrial Technology program. Due to limited space, this paper presents one student's narrated experiences of life and studies. From his story four categories emerge that are related to his choice of the Industrial Technology program.

Keywords

Industrial Technology program, attractiveness of vocational training, newly arrived students, habitus

1 Introduction

Secondary vocational education in Sweden consists of twelve vocational programmes which are three years long and lead to a vocational exam (Swedish National Agency for Education, 2016). Since upper secondary vocational education does not meet the future demand in these areas there is a risk of a shortage of trained workforce, including in industry (SCB, 2018). One of the reasons for the lack of trained labour in industry is that a small number of students apply for the Industrial Technology program. But there is an exception. A survey from the Swedish National Agency for Education (2017) shows that the Industrial Technology program is more attractive than study preparation programs to newly arrived immigrants in Sweden. It is therefore important to study-the reason for choosing the Industrial Technology program stated by the newly arrived students who have already chosen the program and investigate: What categories emerge from the newly arrived students' narratives about their choice of the Industrial Technology program?

2 Attractiveness of vocational training

International research shows that vocational education in European countries has a varied status in relation to university preparatory education. For example, vocational education generally has a high status in countries like Germany, Switzerland, and Austria (Billett, 2011, 2013; Billett & Choy, 2013; Bolli et al., 2018; Borkowsky & Gonon, 1998; Salter et al., 2017). The social class of students, both in Scandinavian countries (Aarkrog, 2020; Anders, 2017; Eiríksdóttir, 2023), and in the other European countries (Atkins & Flint, 2015; Meriläinen et al., 2019), plays an important role in their choice of profession and vocational education. The upper secondary programmes chosen by young people with an immigrant background in Finland are often related to employment opportunities (Brunila et al., 2011; Kalalahti et al., 2017). The attractiveness of vocational education can also be related to ethnicity. Previous research shows that students with an immigrant background in some countries, for example England (Atkins & Flint, 2015; Avis et al., 2017) and Finland (Brunila et al., 2011), are overrepresented in vocational education.

The professions and educational backgrounds of the parents can also stimulate interest in vocational education (Anders, 2017; Hansen, 2011; Paulsen & Haug, 2020). International political events can attract students to a certain vocational education (Pilz et al., 2018), for example in relation to mobility and work within the EU. In addition, students who prefer to work with their hands are often interested in vocational education (Paulsen & Haug, 2020). As regards the Industrial Technology program in Sweden, the status of the education can be related to the status of the vocational school. For example, the international and well-known Swedish industrial companies that conduct industrial education are considered by young people to have a high status, and the Industrial Technology program in those schools thus has a higher power of attraction (Asghari, 2023).

3 Habitus

Theoretically, I proceed from Bourdieu (1977) and Broady (1990) since my claim is that the theory of habitus can help me to understand the narrated life experiences of eight newly arrived students within different time periods, in their home countries and in Sweden. Bourdieu (1977) writes that habitus is a coherent whole of the capital, materials, and resources that are rooted in the individual and carried by the individual all the time. This ingrainedness has developed during the individual's upbringing, since childhood and in his/her social world, and helps him/her to perceive various events taking place in the world, but habitus is also changeable and the change takes place in the interaction between the individual and the social space (Bourdieu, 1985). Each individual carries an indivisible life of experiences that help him/her in interpreting the world, making decisions, and behaving in a certain way (Bourdieu, 1977; Broady, 1990). Habitus is a result of social experiences and collective memories that are carved into the individual's body and mind and cause the individual to move, think, and behave in their own way (Bourdieu, 1986). Habitus guides the individual in his/her actions, mind-set, and orientation in the social world (Bourdieu, 1984).

4 Life course

The methodological starting point in the study is based on a Life course perspective. Life course has its emphasis on life events, transitions, and life trajectories as contextualized processes (Elder et al., 2003; Vogt, 2018). When a life event occurs, the individual goes through a transition as a result of the life event. For individuals, the transition means that they will be in a life path for a longer period of time (Hutchison, 2019). The concept of transition has its origins in contextualized Life course perspectives (Elder et al., 2003). A fundamental assumption in Life course research is that transitions are not single, isolated events, but always embedded in

trajectories that give them distinct form and meaning (cf. Elder et al., 2003; Gee & Elder, 1986). Life events that take place as well as the transitions and life paths that an individual goes through in life, can be decisive factors in the changes that are made in his/her life (Hutchison, 2019) and have significance for how the individual is shaped (Mayer, 2009).

5 Selection of newly arrived students

Through contact with vocational upper secondary schools, I came into contact with two students whom I call Ahmad and Mohsen in my study. Ahmad and Mohsen are from two different schools, in two different cities, and do not know each other. The request for participation in the study was based on the snowball effect (cf. Bryman, 2016) via Ahmad and Mohsen to the other six participating students who lived in different locations in Sweden. Ebrahim, whose story is used in this paper, is one of the eight students.

In the research process, I have relied on the guidelines of the Swedish Research Council (2017). Due to the pandemic, the interviews were conducted online (e.g. via Zoom, FaceTime, WhatsApp) during the years 2020 and 2021. All students were interviewed twice and six of them were interviewed a third time. The two students who were not interviewed a third time were the ones who, despite consent, did not respond to my request for the interview. The length of the first and second interviews was between 45 – 60 minutes and the third interview 30 – 45 minutes. The interview questions were based on the main research topic *newly arrived students' life and professional experiences and their choice of the Industrial Technology program*.

6 Analysis of interviews

I brought together each student's interview data from the first, the second, and the third (of the students who had been interviewed three times) interviews and structured the descriptions chronologically (cf. Lieblich et al., 1998). In other words, I as a researcher created stories from the students' stories (cf. Lieblich, 1993). In my analysis work, in a categorizing approach, I departed from Lieblich et al. (1998) when I divided, defined, sectioned, named, and collected single words that belong to a defined category from my story about young students' accounts of their life and professional experiences. In this way, different categories of the attractiveness of industrial education emerged from the stories.

7 Results

In this short paper, I report only one of the student's narrated experiences of his life and studies. The result highlights four characteristic aspects that are related to his choice of the Industrial Technology program: [1] A good working environment in the Swedish workshop, [2] The good wages of workshop workers, [3] The need for labour in industry, and [4] To be able to get employment with a good income, get a residence permit, and not be deported.

Ebrahim's story

When my father was up on a construction site welding, he fell 20 meters and died, and then my mother and my siblings needed a new breadwinner. [...] I and my brother took over dad's job as a welder [...]. On the days when there was no work on the construction site or in the workshop, we also worked at the boss's house, we usually started very early in the morning and we worked with the housework until 11, 12 o'clock at night. We cleaned, fixed broken things, painted his house. He himself was very rich [...] He himself never worked. There were always others working for him and he treated us like slaves. [...] I was 15 years old when I came to Sweden. [...] I had bad

experiences with the workshop and how my boss treated me [in my home country]. I didn't want to be a slave again, but then we went on a study visit and the boss there was wearing work clothes, just like everyone else, and he himself was working on the floor. But then he also talked to us just as if we were people like him. It was really strange, I wasn't an animal anymore [...]. I also heard that industry needed people and it was easier to get a job and make money and make a living [...]. Then I also saw that the salary is high and the job opportunities were great here and I could get a job and stay in Sweden, otherwise I will be deported to my home country, and I don't want that. Then I also saw that the manager here was also not like my manager in my home country, and then I thought, okay, I choose industry.

Ebrahim's life course (Elder et al., 2003; Hutchison, 2019; Vogt, 2018) is about a life where he as a child worked for a period as a welder in his home country, and about his bad experiences from his job at the workshop and how his boss treated him there. Ebrahim was treated badly by his rich boss when he worked at his house for long hours. It is obvious that Ebrahim's life and professional experiences have been important for his choice of industrial education from the way that he compares his previous experiences of being mistreated with his experiences of the study visit. In his case, the choice of industrial education has become for him the choice of an education that leads to an industrial profession that is in need of labour [3], has a good work environment [1] where a boss treats his employees with dignity, and offers a high salary [2]. It also appears that the choice of the Industrial Technology program was made based on opportunities for employment which in turn should lead to a residence permit and a chance to stay in Sweden [4].

8 Discussion

Newly arrived students carry an indivisible life of life experiences (cf. Bourdieu, 2008), that is, each of them has a life history which can be seen from different perspectives in the human social field and can be placed in families, classes, professional groups, and so on (cf. Bourdieu, 1977; Broady, 1990). The students in this study come from the working class and research shows that working class students choose vocational education to a greater extent (e.g. Aarkrog, 2020; Anders, 2017; Eiríksdóttir, 2023), but in the case of these informants, even if they had come from the middle or upper class, they might still choose the Industrial Technology program. This is due to the requirement for self-sufficiency and labour market establishment for permanent residence permits (Swedish Migration Agency, 2022).

People's habitus is important for their taste, opinion, and thinking, which are context-bound and take shape in the society in which the individual has grown up and in the interaction between the individual, other people, and their social space (Bourdieu, 1985, 1995, 2008). That society, and the working-class families in which the newly arrived students in this study have grown up, have been significant in shaping their taste, opinion, and thinking. Since the students in the study themselves come from the working class, their taste, opinion, and thinking about working with the body are ingrained in them (cf. Bourdieu, 1977). In that context, the students' choice of the Industrial Technology program can be understood based on Bourdieu (1977), in relation to taste, opinion, and thinking related to physical work, but also based on Anders (2017), Hansen (2011), and Paulsen and Haug (2020), in relation to their parents' occupational background as workers. But since taste, opinion, and thinking are also changing, and the change takes place in the interaction between newly arrived students and their social space (cf. Bourdieu, 1985), the importance of further study at the university level, and the idea of becoming an engineer, also become important reasons for the choice of the Industrial technology program in their new country, Sweden.

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Biographical note

Dr **Hamid Asghari** is an Associate Professor at the Department of Educational Studies at Karlstad University in Sweden. His research interests focus on narrative studies, vocational education, newly arrived refugee youths in vocational education, (vocational) teachers' and (vocational) students' life stories. He is active in teacher and vocational teacher education at Karlstad University.